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CLIMATE-RESILIENT RICE CULTIVATION FOR URBAN HOMESTEADS

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Cultivating rice in multi-storeyed flats encounters challenges due to limited space, hindering the typical expansive growth of rice plants. Insufficient sunlight, water supply issues, nutrient management difficulties, and suboptimal temperature and humidity control collectively impede crop growth. The confined spaces exacerbate pest and disease spread, necessitating effective chemical control. Creating support structures for indoor cultivation and harvesting presents challenges that demand innovative solutions. Successful cultivation in such environments requires a thoughtful adaptation of cultivation practices to fit the constraints of container gardening. The study at the Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Kerala Agricultural University, aimed to develop a rice cultivation practice resilient to extreme water, nutrient, and biotic stresses. A growth medium was standardised for the endophytic root-colonizing fungus *Piriformospora indica* for effective colonisation in paddy seedlings. The broth of the fungus was blended with various growth media components, *viz.*, paddy soil, farmyard manure (FYM), vermicompost, neem cake, and coir pith compost in varying proportions in a completely random design with eight treatments and nine replications. The highest and statistically significant levels in various parameters, including germination percentage (92.27%), seedling height (20.50 cm), leaves per plant (2.10), leaf length (15.33 cm), leaf width (3.27 cm), shoot dry weight (0.01 g/plant), dry matter production (0.02 g/plant), root length (9.22 cm), root volume (0.11 cm³), and root dry weight (0.01 g/plant) were recorded for the growth media prepared using paddy soil: FYM: coir pith compost in 1:1:1 ratio. The study underscored the substantial enhancement in rice seedling growth achieved by cultivating the endophyte in a growth medium comprising paddy soil, FYM, and coir pith compost. The growth parameters surpassed those observed under control conditions, emphasising the positive impact of this specific growth medium on rice seedling development.

Key words: Paddy, Nutrient use efficiency, Stress tolerance, Endophyte, *Piriformospora indica*